

THE ROLE OF OMNICHANNEL SERVICE ON LATENT CONSUMER BEHAVIOR WITH PERCEIVED VALUE AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE AT CV EMPAT CAHAYA NOESANTARA

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of Omnichannel Service in activating Latent Consumer Behavior with Perceived Value as an intervening variable at CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara. The research is based on the issue of increasing consumer interactions across digital channels that are not matched by actual conversion from latent consumers into active customers, highlighting the need to understand how Omnichannel Service shapes consumers' Perceived Value. The research uses a quantitative method with Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The sample consists of digital channel users of CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara who have interacted with the platform but have not completed or rarely engaged in transactions. Data were collected through an online questionnaire to examine both direct and indirect relationships among the variables. The results show that Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value and Latent Consumer Behavior. Perceived Value also significantly influences Latent Consumer Behavior and mediates the relationship between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior. These findings emphasize the importance of channel integration, responsiveness, and information quality in enhancing Perceived Value and activating latent consumers.

Keywords: *Omnichannel Service, Perceived Value, Latent Consumer Behavior, SOR.*

INTRODUCTION

The acceleration of digital technology has fundamentally reshaped consumer purchasing behavior, particularly in the way consumers interact with brands across multiple touchpoints. Contemporary consumers no longer rely on a single channel during the decision-making process, but instead engage with various platforms such as websites, mobile applications, social media, and physical stores in an integrated manner. This behavioral shift has encouraged firms to adopt Omnichannel Service strategies, which emphasize the integration and coordination of all communication and distribution channels to deliver a consistent and seamless customer experience (Pranindyasari, 2023). Omnichannel Service has been widely acknowledged as a strategic approach capable of enhancing customer experience through channel integration, interactivity, and personalization. Prior studies indicate that effective omnichannel implementation positively influences brand-related outcomes, including brand choice experience and customer retention (Pranindyasari, 2023). Nevertheless, empirical findings also suggest that omnichannel initiatives do not automatically result in active or loyal consumer behavior. This inconsistency indicates that the effectiveness of omnichannel strategies depends on intermediate psychological mechanisms formed during consumer–brand interactions. Perceived Value represents consumers' overall evaluation of the benefits obtained relative to the costs incurred, including monetary, temporal, and cognitive sacrifices (Zeithaml, 1988). In digital service environments, perceived value extends beyond price considerations and encompasses experiential factors such as system usability, information consistency across channels,

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responsiveness, and service reliability (Wardhana & Pradana, 2023). When consumers perceive higher value during omnichannel interactions, they are more likely to develop favorable behavioral intentions and responses. Despite extensive exposure to digital marketing efforts, many firms continue to face difficulties in converting potential consumers into actual buyers. This condition is often associated with latent consumers—individuals who demonstrate interest through online behaviors such as browsing, searching, or cart abandonment but refrain from completing transactions. According to the Jobs to Be Done perspective (Christensen, 2003), consumer needs are frequently latent and psychological in nature, rendering them less observable through conventional survey-based approaches. Recent empirical evidence further suggests that functional satisfaction alone may be insufficient to stimulate behavioral activation. Auditya Brilliant and Achyar (2023) reported that customer satisfaction does not consistently lead to loyalty, whereas trust and information quality play a more decisive role. Similarly, Wardhana and Pradana (2023) found that perceived value significantly influences brand choice decisions. These findings imply that perceived value serves as a critical psychological mechanism linking service attributes to behavioral outcomes, particularly for consumers who have not yet engaged in actual transactions.

This mechanism is consistent with the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, which posits that external stimuli affect individual behavior through internal cognitive and affective states (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). In the context of this study, Omnichannel Service functions as an external stimulus that shapes consumers' internal evaluations, specifically perceived value, which subsequently drives behavioral responses in the form of Latent Consumer Behavior activation. Within the highly competitive Indonesian e-commerce environment, characterized by low switching costs and high consumer mobility, firms are required to move beyond mere channel integration toward value-driven engagement strategies. CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara, a building materials distributor that has adopted the Bantudagang omnichannel platform, integrates various digital sales channels such as WhatsApp, online marketplaces, and social media. However, fluctuations in social media sales performance indicate that omnichannel integration alone has not been sufficient to ensure consistent purchase conversion, particularly among latent consumers.

Despite the growing body of literature on omnichannel strategies and perceived value, studies that explicitly examine the integrated relationship between Omnichannel Service, Perceived Value, and Latent Consumer Behavior remain limited. Most prior research focuses on the effects of omnichannel strategies on loyalty or the role of perceived value in brand choice, with limited attention to the latent consumer segment. Addressing this gap is essential, given the substantial potential of latent consumers to be activated through strategically designed omnichannel experiences. Accordingly, this study aims to examine the effect of Omnichannel Service on Latent Consumer Behavior, with Perceived Value serving as a mediating variable, using the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework. This research is expected to contribute empirically to digital marketing and consumer behavior literature by providing a more nuanced understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying omnichannel effectiveness, particularly in activating latent consumers. Based on the theoretical framework and empirical evidence discussed above, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior.

H2: Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value.

H3: Perceived Value has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior.

H4: Perceived Value mediates the relationship between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Grand Theory (Stimulus–Organism–Response)

The Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) theory explains that individual behavior is shaped through internal psychological processes that arise after exposure to external stimuli (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). Behavior does not occur instantly, but is mediated by cognitive and affective evaluations within the individual. In this study, Omnichannel Service acts as the stimulus representing integrated service interactions across digital platforms. These stimuli are processed internally by consumers in the form of Perceived Value, which reflects cognitive and emotional evaluation. The final response is reflected in Latent Consumer Behavior, representing consumers who engage but have not yet converted into active buyers. The SOR framework is therefore relevant to explain consumer behavior in omnichannel environments.

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Omnichannel Service

Omnichannel Service refers to the strategic integration of multiple communication and transaction channels to create a seamless customer experience. Unlike multichannel systems, omnichannel emphasizes consistency, synchronization, and real-time interaction across platforms (Payne et al., 2017). In digital business contexts, effective omnichannel service improves accessibility, responsiveness, and information consistency, which enhances consumer confidence. For small and medium enterprises, omnichannel platforms such as Bantudagang function as technological enablers that connect marketplaces, social media, and chat-based services into a unified system, supporting consumer engagement and service efficiency.

Perceived Value

Perceived Value is defined as consumers' overall evaluation of the benefits received relative to the sacrifices made during service interaction (Zeithaml, 1988). In omnichannel environments, perceived value is not limited to price considerations, but also includes convenience, service responsiveness, trust, and ease of use. Within the SOR framework, Perceived Value represents the organism that mediates the influence of omnichannel stimuli on consumer behavior. When consumers perceive high value from integrated services, they are more likely to progress from passive interaction to purchase intention.

Latent Consumer Behavior

Latent Consumer Behavior refers to consumers who demonstrate interest, engagement, or interaction with a brand but have not completed transactions. These consumers typically remain in the consideration stage of the decision-making process and represent high conversion potential. In omnichannel settings, latent consumers are influenced by service quality, perceived value, and psychological assurance. Improving service integration and value perception is therefore critical to activating latent consumers and encouraging behavioral transition toward active purchasing.

Relationship Between Variable

Omnichannel Service is expected to directly influence Latent Consumer Behavior by reducing uncertainty and improving service convenience. Additionally, Omnichannel Service enhances Perceived Value through consistent information, integrated communication, and responsive service. Perceived Value is hypothesized to mediate the relationship between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior. Higher perceived value strengthens consumer confidence and motivation, increasing the likelihood of behavioral conversion. Thus, Perceived Value functions as a key internal mechanism that determines the effectiveness of omnichannel strategies.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design that aims to explain the causal relationship between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior, with Perceived Value as an intervening variable, through testing previously formulated hypotheses. The quantitative approach was selected because it enables objective measurement of the effects of omnichannel service on latent consumer behavior through numerical data collection and statistical analysis (Sugiyono, 2017). The population in this study consists of latent consumers of CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara who have interacted with the company through digital channels but have not consistently completed purchase transactions. These interactions include viewing product pages, adding items to cart, communicating via WhatsApp Business, or following the company's official social media accounts. Because the exact population size is not known with certainty, the sampling technique used is convenience sampling. The sample size was determined using the rule of thumb proposed by Hair et al. (2019), namely multiplying the total number of indicators by 5–10. With 13 indicators, a total of 104 respondents were obtained and considered sufficient for analysis. The data collection instrument used in this study was a closed-ended questionnaire distributed online using Google Forms. The questionnaire was developed based on indicators of each variable derived from the theoretical framework. Each statement item was measured using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". This scale was chosen because it is effective in measuring respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and evaluations toward the research variables in a structured manner (Sugiyono, 2017). The variables examined in this study consist of Omnichannel Service (X) as the independent variable, Perceived Value (Z) as the intervening variable, and Latent Consumer Behavior (Y) as the dependent variable. The operational definitions of these variables were adopted from established theories, including

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omnichannel integration theory (Verhoef et al., 2015), perceived value theory (Zeithaml, 1988), and latent consumer behavior concepts (Christensen, 2003; Nugroho & Firdaus, 2022). The data analysis technique employed in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Squares (PLS) using SmartPLS software. This technique was chosen because it is capable of analyzing complex relationships among latent variables with a relatively small sample size and does not require normally distributed data. The analysis was conducted in two stages: evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) to assess the validity and reliability of indicators, and evaluation of the structural model (inner model) to test the relationships among constructs, including the coefficient of determination (R^2), path coefficients, and mediation effects (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). By employing this methodological approach, the study is expected to provide a clear explanation of the direct and indirect effects of omnichannel service on latent consumer behavior, as well as to clarify the mediating role of perceived value. The SEM-PLS approach is considered the most appropriate method for this study because it is able to handle complex research models and data characteristics commonly found in field survey research.

Framework of thought

This study conducts testing and analysis using **three variables**, namely **Omnichannel Service (X)** as the independent variable, **Perceived Value (Z)** as the intervening variable, and **Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)** as the dependent variable. Based on the research framework presented above, this study aims to examine both the **direct effect** of Omnichannel Service on Latent Consumer Behavior and the **indirect effect** through Perceived Value as a mediating mechanism.

The framework is grounded in the **Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) theory** and **consumer psychology theory**, where Omnichannel Service acts as an external stimulus that influences consumers' internal evaluations in the form of Perceived Value, which subsequently shapes their behavioral responses. In this context, Latent Consumer Behavior represents consumer responses that indicate potential activation from passive to active engagement. Through this framework, the study analyzes how Omnichannel Service implemented by CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara directly influences Latent Consumer Behavior and how this relationship is strengthened through Perceived Value as an intervening variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Profile

The description of respondents indicates that the majority are male (67.3%), while female respondents account for 32.7%. In terms of age, respondents are predominantly within the early to mid-30s, with the most dominant age groups being 32 and 33 years old (each 9.6%), indicating that most respondents are in the productive adult age range. Based on

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occupational background, the respondents are mainly private-sector employees (63.5%), followed by entrepreneurs or self-employed individuals (28.8%), while the remaining respondents work as civil servants or in other occupations. Regarding educational background, most respondents hold a Bachelor's degree (S1) at 54.8%, followed by vocational education graduates (35.6%), indicating that the majority of respondents have attained higher education.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity testing was conducted using the outer model in PLS-SEM, including convergent validity (outer loadings ≥ 0.70 , or ≥ 0.50 for exploratory research) and discriminant validity assessed through AVE (> 0.50) and cross-loading values. Reliability was evaluated using Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha, with values exceeding 0.70, indicating adequate construct reliability. After meeting all validity and reliability criteria, the inner model was assessed using R-square (R^2), path coefficient significance, and indirect effect testing to examine the mediating role of Perceived Value between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior.

Picture 1: PLS Model

Source: processed by researchers (2025)

Outer Model

At the outer model testing stage, the convergent validity test results show that all indicators have loading factor values above 0.50, indicating that each indicator adequately represents its construct and no indicators need to be eliminated. In addition, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs are above 0.50, confirming good convergent validity. Furthermore, the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values for all variables exceed the threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Therefore, the measurement model is valid and reliable and can be continued to the inner model testing stage.

Inner Model

Testing of the structural model was conducted by examining the R-Square values to assess the model's explanatory power. The R-Square value for Perceived Value (Z) is 0.720, indicating that Omnichannel Service explains 72.0% of its variance. Meanwhile, the R-Square value for Latent Consumer Behavior (Y) is 0.740, indicating that Omnichannel Service and Perceived Value jointly explain 74.0% of the variance in Latent Consumer Behavior. These results indicate that the structural model has strong explanatory power and is suitable for hypothesis testing.

Table 1. R-Square Results

R-Square Overview

	R Square	
<i>Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)</i>	0,740	<i>Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)</i>
<i>Perceived Value (Z)</i>	0,720	<i>Perceived Value (Z)</i>

Source: Processed Data (2025)

In the inner model test, it is found that the R-square value for Latent Consumer Behavior is 0.740. This indicates that the combination of Omnichannel Service and Perceived Value is able to explain 74.0% of the variance in Latent Consumer Behavior. Meanwhile, the remaining 26.0% is explained by other variables that are not included in this research model. Furthermore, the R-square value for Perceived Value is 0.720, which means that Omnichannel Service is able to explain 72.0% of the variance in Perceived Value. The remaining 28.0% is influenced by other factors outside the scope of the model examined in this study.

Hypothesis Testing

In hypothesis testing, two tests are carried out, namely direct influence and indirect influence tests

Table 2 Results of Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

Path coefficients

STDEV, T values, p values

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Omnichannel Service (X) -> Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)	0,319	2,590	0,010
Omnichannel Service (X) -> Perceived Value (Z)	0,848	17,674	0,000
Perceived Value (Z) -> Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)	0,573	4,721	0,000

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table above, the results of hypothesis testing H1, H2, and H3 can be described as follows:

1. In H1: Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior, with a path coefficient of 0.319. The p-value of 0.010 is smaller than the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), indicating a statistically significant effect. Therefore, it can be concluded that Omnichannel Service (X) has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior (Y), so H1 is accepted.
2. In H2: Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value, with a path coefficient of 0.848. The p-value of 0.000 is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), indicating a highly significant effect. This result shows that Omnichannel Service (X) positively influences Perceived Value (Z). Thus, H2 is accepted.
3. In H3: Perceived Value has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior, with a path coefficient of 0.573. The p-value of 0.000 is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), indicating a significant effect. Therefore, it can be stated that Perceived Value (Z) has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior (Y), so H3 is accepted.

The next test is the indirect effect test. The following are the results of the indirect effect test of this study:

Table 3 Results of Indirect Effect Hypothesis Test

**Specific indirect effects
STDEV, T values, p value**

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Omnichannel Service (X) -> Perceived Value (Z) -> Latent Consumer Behavior (Y)	0,486	4,294	0,000

Source: Processed Data (2025)

4. **In H4: Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior through Perceived Value**, with a path coefficient of **0.486**. The p-value of **0.000** is smaller than the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), indicating a statistically significant indirect effect. Therefore, it can be stated that **Perceived Value mediates the effect of Omnichannel Service on Latent Consumer Behavior**, so **H4 is accepted**.

Discussion

The Influence of Omnichannel Service on Perceived Value

Based on the results of data analysis, the hypothesis states that Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value. The testing results indicate that Omnichannel Service has a path coefficient of 0.848 with a p-value of 0.000, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 is accepted. This finding indicates that better channel integration, information consistency, and service convenience implemented by CV Empat Cahaya Noesantara through the Bantudagang platform lead to higher perceived value among consumers. Theoretically, this result supports the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, in which Omnichannel Service acts as an external stimulus that triggers consumers’ internal evaluation processes (organism) in the form of perceived benefits, convenience, and overall value. When consumers experience seamless cross-channel interactions, stable systems, and responsive services, their perceived value increases significantly.

This finding is consistent with previous studies. Ariyanti et al. (2023) found that system convenience and consistent digital content positively influence perceived value and brand image, which subsequently affect purchase decisions. Hendrati et al. (2023) also emphasized that perceived value is formed through service interaction quality and efficient digital experiences. Furthermore, Febrian (2025) demonstrated that personalization and technological consistency significantly enhance consumers’ perceived value. Thus, the relationship between Omnichannel Service and Perceived Value in this study is supported both statistically and theoretically.

The Influence of Omnichannel Service on Latent Consumer Behavior

The results of the analysis indicate that Omnichannel Service has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior, with a path coefficient of 0.319 and a p-value of 0.010. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is accepted. This result suggests that improvements in omnichannel experience not only generate positive perceptions but also encourage latent consumers to engage in exploratory behaviors, such as revisiting channels, searching for additional information, and considering purchase decisions. This finding aligns with the SOR framework, which explains that external stimuli in the form of integrated services can directly generate behavioral responses without necessarily passing through evaluative stages first. It is also consistent with the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which states that positive experiences shape favorable attitudes and behavioral tendencies. From the perspective of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), improved omnichannel service enhances perceived behavioral control, making the purchasing process feel easier and more manageable, thereby encouraging consumer behavior.

Previous studies support this result. Prasetyo et al. (2022) found that integrated digital marketing activities increase consumer responses through higher awareness and engagement. Hardiyanto and Firdaus (2021) also confirmed that system convenience and digital channel quality significantly affect behavioral intentions in e-commerce contexts. Additionally, Rizano and Salehudin (2023) showed that attractive, interactive, and user-friendly digital experiences encourage consumer engagement and follow-up behaviors. Thus, this study reinforces evidence that Omnichannel Service can directly influence behavioral changes, particularly among latent consumers.

The Influence of Perceived Value on Latent Consumer Behavior

The results indicate that Perceived Value has a positive and significant effect on Latent Consumer Behavior, with a path coefficient of 0.573 and a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is accepted. This finding implies that higher perceived value derived from the Bantudagang platform increases the likelihood that consumers will exhibit latent behaviors such as exploration, revisit intention, and purchase consideration. From a theoretical perspective, this result supports the SOR framework, in which perceived value represents the organism component that precedes behavioral responses. When consumers perceive high functional, emotional, and convenience-related value, they are more likely to engage in consumption-related behaviors even if they have not yet completed a transaction. This is further explained by TRA, which views perceived value as a determinant of positive attitudes, and TPB, which emphasizes that perceived benefits and ease of use strengthen behavioral intentions. This finding is consistent with previous research. Wardhana and Pradana (2023) found that perceived value and digital service reputation strongly influence consumers' brand choice behavior. Hendrati et al. (2023) also reported that perceived value significantly determines repurchase intention in service industries. Moreover, Febrian (2025) demonstrated that perceived value acts as a key mediator linking technology quality to consumer behavior. Therefore, this study confirms that Perceived Value is a critical factor in activating latent consumer behavior.

The Influence of Omnichannel Service on Latent Consumer Behavior through Perceived Value

The mediation test results indicate that Perceived Value significantly mediates the relationship between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior, with an indirect effect value of 0.486 and a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, Hypothesis 4 is accepted. This result shows that Omnichannel Service does not only influence behavior directly, but exerts a stronger effect when processed through consumers' perceived value. Theoretically, this finding represents an ideal application of the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, in which external stimuli influence behavioral responses through internal psychological evaluations. The mediating role of perceived value strengthens the argument that consumer behavior is driven not merely by service experiences, but by the meaning and benefits consumers attribute to those experiences.

This result is consistent with prior studies. Ariyanti et al. (2023) found that perceived value mediates the relationship between system quality and purchase behavior. Roswita Bupu et al. (2023) also identified consumer perception as a key mediator between service quality and satisfaction. Furthermore, Febrian (2025) demonstrated that brand equity—conceptually similar to perceived value—mediates the influence of AI-based technology on purchase intention. Overall, these findings confirm that all hypothesized relationships in this study are significant and aligned with established theories and previous empirical evidence. This study contributes theoretically by emphasizing that activating latent consumers requires not only integrated omnichannel services, but also the formation of strong perceived value. Perceived Value thus functions as a key psychological mechanism that transforms latent consumers into more active participants within an omnichannel service context.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion in the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Omnichannel Service is empirically proven to have a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value. Consistent channel integration, ease of access, and aligned service experiences enable consumers to perceive greater benefits and convenience when using the platform.
2. Omnichannel Service contributes to the activation of Latent Consumer Behavior. A seamless, responsive, and integrated service experience encourages latent consumers to re-engage with the platform, seek additional information, and exhibit more active consumption-related behaviors.
3. Perceived Value plays a crucial role in enhancing Latent Consumer Behavior. When consumers perceive high value from digital services, they become more interested, demonstrate higher revisit intentions, and show greater readiness to engage in usage and purchasing activities.
4. Perceived Value functions as the primary mediating mechanism between Omnichannel Service and Latent Consumer Behavior. Well-implemented omnichannel services first shape consumers' perceived value, which subsequently drives behavioral changes from passive to more active engagement.

Overall, the findings confirm that the implementation of Omnichannel Service plays a vital role in enhancing both perceived value and consumer behavior. Effective system integration not only improves operational efficiency but also

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strengthens emotional connections between consumers and firms, ultimately increasing consumers' willingness to engage and their willingness to pay for digital services such as Bantudagang.

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